

Paper_visualisations

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Description

Code used to generate paper figures. dpi 300 versions of all figures were generated and compiled in powerpoint. Note code is optimised for final figures, not a knitted Rmarkdown pdf, so some plots will not be visually pleasing in this knitted R document.

Required packages

```
library(pacman)
p_load(TCseq, hdWGCNA, enrichplot, ggsci, tidyverse, tidyr, clusterProfiler,
       readr, readxl, viridis, cluster, patchwork, gplots, ggplot2,
       ggrepel, DOSE, patchwork, grid, pdftools)
# need to ensure that dplyr is loaded last or things get
# funky
p_unload(dplyr)
p_load(dplyr)
```

Figure 1

1A: HPO enrichments

read in gene lists (entrez IDs)

```
# read in the gene lists:
SNV_psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_SNV_psych.txt")
SNV_neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_SNV_neurol.txt")
SNV_neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_SNV_neurodev.txt")
GWAS_psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_GWAS_psych.txt")
GWAS_neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_GWAS_neurol.txt")
GWAS_neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/entrez_gene_list_GWAS_neurodev.txt")
geneLists <- list(SNV_psych = SNV_psych, SNV_neurol = SNV_neurol,
                 SNV_neurodev = SNV_neurodev, GWAS_psych = GWAS_psych, GWAS_neurol = GWAS_neurol,
                 GWAS_neurodev = GWAS_neurodev)
background <- unique(unlist(geneLists))
```

HPO enrichments


```

ggsave(file = "./results/paper_visualisations/1ACuratedDisGenes_HPO_enrich.pdf",
  p, width = 10, height = 12, dpi = 300)
# rm(ck, xx, p)

```

1B: DisGeneNET enrichments

```

ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters = geneLists, fun = "enrichDGN",
  pAdjustMethod = "BH", pvalueCutoff = 0.05, universe = background,
  readable = TRUE)
ck <- setReadable(ck, OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db", keyType = "ENTREZID")
ck@compareClusterResult <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
  filter(Count > 5)

xx <- pairwise_termsim(ck)
p <- emaplot(xx, cex_category = 1.5)
p

```



```
ggsave(file = "./results/paper_visualisations/1BCuratedDisGenes_DGN_enrich.pdf",
       p, width = 10, height = 12, dpi = 300)
rm(list = ls())
```

1C,D: Jaccard scoring of HPO/DisGeNET terms enriched in the curated disorder-type specific gene lists (Neurodevelopmental, Neurological and Psychiatric)

```
# Load curated disorder-type specific gene lists
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")
neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurol_allgenes_list.txt")
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/psych_allgenes_list.txt")

# Curated gene lists as a named list
curated_lists <- list(Neurodevelopmental = as.numeric(neurodev),
                     Neurological = as.numeric(neurol), Psychiatric = as.numeric(psych))

# Read in HPO2gene data to align with enriched HPO terms
phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("./HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt") %>%
  dplyr::select(-disease_id) %>%
  distinct()

id_to_gene <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, ncbi_gene_id)

# Load HPO enrichments
HPO_enrich <- read_csv("./scratch/sanitycheck/enrichments/neuropsych_genelist_enrichments_HPO_0.05padj_1")
HPO_descriptions <- HPO_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)
HPO_terms <- HPO_enrich$ID

# Load DisGeNET enrichments
DGN_enrich <- read_csv("./scratch/sanitycheck/enrichments/neuropsych_genelist_enrichments_DGN_0.05padj_1")
DGN_descriptions <- DGN_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)
DGN_terms <- DGN_enrich$ID

# Process DisGeNET Enrichment with Full Gene List for Each
# Term
data("DGN_PATHID2EXTID")
large_list_df <- map_df(names(DGN_PATHID2EXTID), ~tibble(ID = .x,
  Genes = list(DGN_PATHID2EXTID[[.x]])))
DGN_results <- large_list_df %>%
  filter(ID %in% DGN_terms) %>%
  unnest(cols = Genes) %>%
  mutate(ENTREZID = as.numeric(Genes)) %>%
  select(-Genes)

# Filter id_to_gene for relevant HPO terms
HPO_gene_lists <- id_to_gene %>%
  filter(hpo_id %in% HPO_terms) %>%
```

```

    rename(Source = hpo_id, ENTREZID = ncbi_gene_id)

DGN_results <- DGN_results %>%
  rename(Source = ID)

# Function to calculate Jaccard index
calculate_jaccard_index <- function(genes1, genes2) {
  genes1_set <- unique(genes1)
  genes2_set <- unique(genes2)
  intersection <- length(intersect(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  union <- length(union(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  jaccard_index <- ifelse(union == 0, 0, intersection/union)
  return(jaccard_index)
}

# Function to calculate Jaccard scores for all lists for
# each term
calculate_jaccard_for_term <- function(term_genes, gene_lists) {
  scores <- sapply(gene_lists, function(gene_list) calculate_jaccard_index(term_genes,
    gene_list))
  return(scores)
}

# Function to assign terms to primary enriched gene list
# based on Cluster column
assign_primary_list <- function(enrichment_data) {
  enrichment_data %>%
    mutate(PrimaryList = case_when(grepl("neurodev", Cluster,
      ignore.case = TRUE) ~ "Neurodevelopmental", grepl("neuro",
      Cluster, ignore.case = TRUE) ~ "Neurological", grepl("psych",
      Cluster, ignore.case = TRUE) ~ "Psychiatric", TRUE ~
      NA_character_))
}

# Process enrichments and calculate Jaccard scores
process_enrichments <- function(enrichment_data, gene_lists) {
  enrichment_data %>%
    group_by(Source) %>%
    summarise(JaccardScores = list(calculate_jaccard_for_term(unique(ENTREZID),
      gene_lists)), .groups = "drop") %>%
    unnest_wider(JaccardScores, names_sep = "_")
}

# Process the enrichments for HPO and DisGeNET
hpo_results <- process_enrichments(HPO_gene_lists, curated_lists) %>%
  left_join(HPO_enrich %>%
    select(ID, Cluster, Description), by = c(Source = "ID")) %>%
  assign_primary_list()

dgn_results <- process_enrichments(DGN_results, curated_lists) %>%
  left_join(DGN_enrich %>%
    select(ID, Cluster, Description), by = c(Source = "ID")) %>%
  assign_primary_list()

```

Create plots

```
# Improved label and plot clarity
create_plots <- function(results, enrichment_source) {
  plot_list <- list()

  results_long <- results %>%
    pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("JaccardScores_"), names_to = "GeneList", values_to = "JaccardScore")
    mutate(GeneList = str_replace(GeneList, "JaccardScores_", ""))

  for (primary_list in unique(results$PrimaryList)) {
    subset_results <- results_long %>%
      filter(PrimaryList == primary_list)

    # Identify the top 2-3 terms with the highest Jaccard scores in the primary list
    top_terms <- subset_results %>%
      filter(GeneList == primary_list) %>%
      top_n(2, JaccardScore)

    # Extract the top terms and use them to filter the original dataset for labeling
    labeled_terms <- subset_results %>%
      filter(Source %in% top_terms$Source)

    p <- ggplot(subset_results, aes(x = GeneList, y = JaccardScore, color = GeneList)) +
      geom_jitter(alpha = 0.3, size = 3, width = 0.2) +
      geom_violin(alpha = 0.9) +
      geom_label_repel(data = labeled_terms, aes(label = Description),
        size = 2.5, # Reduced font size
        color = "black", fontface = "bold",
        box.padding = 0.7, point.padding = 1.0,
        segment.curvature = 0.2, # Slight curve to segments
        segment.angle = 20,
        segment.ncp = 3, segment.size = 0.5, segment.color = "grey50",
        force = 5, force_pull = 2, min.segment.length = 0.15
      ) +
      labs(
        title = NULL,
        subtitle = paste(primary_list, enrichment_source, "Enrichments"),
        x = NULL,
        y = "Jaccard Score"
      ) +
      theme_minimal() +
      theme(
        axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 30, hjust = 1, size = 12),
        plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 14), # Correctly place plot.subtitle styling
        axis.title.y = element_text(size = 16),
        axis.text = element_text(size = 14),
        legend.position = "none",
        plot.margin = unit(c(1, 1, 1, 1), "cm")
      ) +
      scale_color_manual(values = c("Neurodevelopmental" = "#E66100",
        "Neurological" = "#5D3A9B",
        "Psychiatric" = "#15D3FF"))
  }
}
```

```

    plot_list[[primary_list]] <- p
  }

  return(plot_list)
}

```

Combining the plots

```

p_load(patchwork)
# Generate and store the plots for HPO
hpo_plots <- create_plots(hpo_results, "HPO")

# Create individual plots with specific titles
hpo_plots[[1]] <- hpo_plots[[1]] + labs(title = "Neurodevelopmental: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))
hpo_plots[[2]] <- hpo_plots[[2]] + labs(title = "Neurological: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))
hpo_plots[[3]] <- hpo_plots[[3]] + labs(title = "Psychiatric: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))

# Combine plots into a single row with a unified title and
# improved layout
hpo_combined <- (hpo_plots[[1]] | hpo_plots[[2]] | hpo_plots[[3]]) +
  plot_annotation(title = "Jaccard Scores for HPO Terms Enriched in the Disorder-Specific Gene Lists"
  subtitle = "A comparison across disorder-specific gene lists",
  theme = theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 18, face = "bold",
  hjust = 0.5), plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 14,
  hjust = 0.5))) & theme(plot.margin = margin(10, 10,
  10, 10))

# Save the combined plot with adjusted width and height
ggsave("./results/paper_visualisations/1C_Disgenes_jaccard_HPO_combined_plots.pdf",
  hpo_combined, width = 15, height = 7.5, limitsize = FALSE)
print(hpo_combined)

```

Jaccard Scores for HPO Terms Enriched in the Disorder-Specific

A comparison across disorder-specific gene lists

Neurodevelopmental: Enriched Terms | Neurological: Enriched Terms | Psychiatric: Enriched Terms


```
# Generate and store the plots for DisGeNET
dgn_plots <- create_plots(dgn_results, "DisGeNET")

# Ensure the plots are correctly identified and ordered
neurodevelopmental_plot <- dgn_plots[[2]]
neurological_plot <- dgn_plots[[1]]
psychiatric_plot <- dgn_plots[[3]]

# Reorder the plots if necessary based on their content or
# original identification Verify which plot corresponds to
# each disorder-specific gene list

# Create individual plots with specific titles for DisGeNET
neurodevelopmental_plot <- neurodevelopmental_plot + labs(title = "Neurodevelopmental: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))
neurological_plot <- neurological_plot + labs(title = "Neurological: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))
psychiatric_plot <- psychiatric_plot + labs(title = "Psychiatric: Enriched Terms",
  subtitle = NULL) + theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 14,
  face = "bold"))

# Combine DisGeNET plots into a single layout
dgn_combined <- (neurodevelopmental_plot | neurological_plot |
  psychiatric_plot) + plot_annotation(title = "Jaccard Scores for DisGeNET Terms Enriched in the Disorder-Specific Gene Lists")
```

```

subtitle = "A comparison across disorder-specific gene lists",
theme = theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 18, face = "bold",
      hjust = 0.5), plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 14,
      hjust = 0.5))) & theme(plot.margin = margin(10, 10, 10,
10))
print(dgn_combined)

```

Plots for DisGeNET Terms Enriched in the Disorder-Specific

A comparison across disorder-specific gene lists


```

# Save the combined DisGeNET plot
ggsave("./results/paper_visualisations/1D_DisGeNET_disgenes_jaccard_combined.pdf",
      dgn_combined, width = 15, height = 7.5, limitsize = FALSE)

```

Make master gene lists for enriched terms from HPO/DisGeNET and examine overlap to curated disorder-type specific gene lists

1. extract genes from enriched terms

```

# Extract genes from enriched DisGeNET terms
dgn_master_genes <- unique(DGN_results$ENTREZID)

# Extract genes from enriched HPO terms
hpo_master_genes <- unique(HPO_gene_lists$ENTREZID)

```

2. Combine master gene lists with curated gene lists

```

# Curated gene lists as a named list
curated_lists <- list(Neurodevelopmental = as.numeric(neurodev),
  Neurological = as.numeric(neurol), Psychiatric = as.numeric(psych),
  DisGeNET = dgn_master_genes, HPO = hpo_master_genes)

```

3. Generate upset plot

```

p_load(UpSetR)

# Prepare data for UpSet plot
gene_list_df <- as.data.frame(matrix(0, nrow = length(unique(unlist(curated_lists))),
  ncol = length(curated_lists)))
colnames(gene_list_df) <- names(curated_lists)
rownames(gene_list_df) <- unique(unlist(curated_lists))

for (list_name in names(curated_lists)) {
  gene_list_df[rownames(gene_list_df) %in% curated_lists[[list_name]],
    list_name] <- 1
}

# Generate UpSet plot
upset(gene_list_df, sets = names(curated_lists), order.by = "freq")

```



```
png(filename = "upset_plot.png", width = 1500, height = 1000,
     res = 150)
upset(gene_list_df, sets = names(curated_lists), order.by = "freq",
      text.scale = 1.5, mainbar.y.label = "Number of Genes", sets.x.label = "Gene List Size")
dev.off()
```

```
## pdf
## 2
```

Figure 2

2A,D: enrichment tiles

```
outdir <- "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust"

DGN_enrichments <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "/20240606_DGN_summary.csv"))

terms <- c("Absent speech", "Muscle hypotonia", "Parkinsonian Disorders",
          "Dystonia Disorders", "MAJOR AFFECTIVE DISORDER 1", "Impulsive Behavior",
          "Progressive supranuclear palsy", "Drug Dependence")

all_caps_label <- "MAJOR AFFECTIVE DISORDER 1"
corrected_label <- "Major Affective Disorder 1"

data <- DGN_enrichments %>%
  filter(Description %in% terms) %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " ")) %>%
  mutate(Description = ifelse(Description == all_caps_label,
                              corrected_label, Description))

# Add cluster size information: need cluster size for: will
# do this manually. VIP cluster 11 (1), PN-dev cluster 7
# (1), SST- cluster 12 (4), SST cluster 7 (2)
clusterSizes <- c("(689 genes)", "(808 genes)", "(560 genes)",
                  "(560 genes)", "(560 genes)", "(560 genes)", "(554 genes)",
                  "(554 genes)")
data <- data %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "), combined_label = paste(cell_type,
                                        clusterSizes, sep = " - "), label_with_break = gsub(" - ",
                                        " \n", combined_label)) # Combine cell_type with extra data
unique_labels <- unique(data$label_with_break)
data$label_with_break <- factor(data$label_with_break, levels = sort(unique(data$label_with_break)))

plot <- ggplot(data = data, aes(x = label_with_break, y = Description,
                               fill = "seagreen")) + geom_tile(width = 1) + theme_classic() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1,
                                    size = 18), axis.text.y = element_text(size = 18), plot.title = element_text(size = 24,
                                                            face = "bold", vjust = 1), legend.position = "none",
        plot.title.position = "plot", plot.margin = unit(c(0.2,
```

```

    0.75, 0, 0.75), "inches")) + ggtitle("DisGeNET enrichments in temporal gene clusters") +
ylab(NULL) + xlab(NULL) + scale_x_discrete(expand = c(0,
0)) + scale_y_discrete(expand = c(0, 0)) + scale_y_discrete(labels = label_wrap_gen(width = 20)) +
geom_hline(yintercept = rep(1:length(unique(data$Description)),
each = 2) - 0.5, linewidth = 0.8) + geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1,
to = length(unique(data$cell_type)), by = 5) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.8) +
geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1, to = length(unique(data$cell_type)),
by = 1) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.1) + scale_x_discrete()

```

plot

DisGeNET enrichments in temporal gene clusters


```

ggsave(plot, filename = "./results/paper_visualisations/2A_DGN_enrichment_tile.pdf",
width = 12, height = 10, dpi = 300)

```

```

outdir <- "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust"

```

```

HPO_enrichments <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "/20240606_HPO_summary.csv"))

```

```

terms <- c("Sleep disturbance", "Delayed speech and language development",

```

```

"Restricted or repetitive behaviors or interests", "Abnormal communication",
"Microcephaly", "Abnormal autonomic nervous system morphology",
"Abnormality of enteric nervous system morphology")

data <- HPO_enrichments %>%
  filter(Description %in% terms) %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "))
# Add cluster size information: need cluster size for: ID2
# cluster 3, PN_dev cluster 11 (4 rows), Astro cluster 5
# (2)- given small number of rows, will just do manually.
clusterSizes <- c("(572 genes)", "(415 genes)", "(415 genes)",
  "(415 genes)", "(415 genes)", "(562 genes)", "(562 genes)")
data <- data %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "), combined_label = paste(cell_type,
    clusterSizes, sep = " - "), label_with_break = gsub(" - ",
    " \n", combined_label)) # Combine cell_type with extra data
unique_labels <- unique(data$label_with_break)
data$label_with_break <- factor(data$label_with_break, levels = sort(unique(data$label_with_break)))

plot <- ggplot(data = data, aes(x = label_with_break, y = Description,
  fill = "seagreen")) + geom_tile(width = 1) + theme_classic() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1,
    size = 18), axis.text.y = element_text(size = 18), plot.title = element_text(size = 24,
    face = "bold", vjust = 1), legend.position = "none",
    plot.title.position = "plot", plot.margin = unit(c(0.2,
    0.75, 0, 0.75), "inches")) + ggtitle("HPO term enrichments in temporal gene clusters") +
  ylab(NULL) + xlab(NULL) + scale_x_discrete(expand = c(0,
  0)) + scale_y_discrete(expand = c(0, 0)) + scale_y_discrete(labels = label_wrap_gen(width = 25)) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = rep(1:length(unique(data$Description)),
    each = 2) - 0.5, linewidth = 0.8) + geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1,
  to = length(unique(data$cell_type)), by = 5) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.8) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1, to = length(unique(data$cell_type)),
    by = 1) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.1) + scale_x_discrete()

plot

```

HPO term enrichments in temporal gene clusters


```
ggsave(plot, filename = paste0("./results/paper_visualisations/2D_HPO_enrichment_tile.pdf"),
        width = 12, height = 10, dpi = 300)
rm(list = ls())
```

2B,E: Jaccard scoring of disease gene lists in clusters.

1. For SST cells

Read in SST gene lists for TCSeq clusters, curated disease gene lists and DisGeNET term gene lists for terms enriched in SST clusters.

```
# SST TCSeq cluster info:
clusterinfo <- read.csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/SST/SST_clusterinfo.csv")
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, Cluster = cluster)
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, cluster_size = num_genes)
SST_Geneinfo <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/SST/SST_Geneinfo.csv")

# Curated gene lists
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")
```

```

neuro1 <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neuro1_allgenes_list.txt")
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
# Combine the gene lists into a single data frame with a
# 'ListName' column
gene_lists <- tibble(ENTREZID = as.numeric(c(neurodev, neuro1,
  psych)), ListName = c(rep("Neurodevelopmental", length(neurodev)),
  rep("Neurological", length(neuro1)), rep("Psychiatric", length(psych))))

```

```

disgeneinfo <- read_tsv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/SST/240424_SST_clusters_d
clusterinfo <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/SST/SST_clusterinfo.csv")
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, Cluster = cluster)
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, cluster_size = num_genes)
cluster_dis_info <- merge(clusterinfo, disgeneinfo, by = "Cluster")

```

```

# Load the DisGeNET enrichments
DGN_enrich <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/20240606_DGN_summary.csv")
SST_subset <- DGN_enrich[grepl("^SST", DGN_enrich$Cluster), ]

# Prepare DGN gene lists
DGN_descriptions <- DGN_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)
SST_DGN_terms <- SST_subset$ID

# Process DGN Enrichment with Full Gene List for Each Term
data("DGN_PATHID2EXTID")
large_list_df <- map_df(names(DGN_PATHID2EXTID), ~tibble(ID = .x,
  Genes = list(DGN_PATHID2EXTID[[.x]])))
DGN_results_TCSeq <- large_list_df %>%
  filter(ID %in% SST_DGN_terms) %>%
  mutate(Genes = map_chr(Genes, ~paste(.x, collapse = "|")))

# DGN_results_TCSeq$GeneSymbols <-
# sapply(strsplit(as.character(DGN_results_TCSeq$Genes),
# '\\|'), map_entrez_to_symbol)
DGN_results_TCSeq <- DGN_results_TCSeq %>%
  left_join(DGN_descriptions, by = "ID")

rm(DGN_enrich, DGN_descriptions, DGN_PATHID2EXTID)

```

Calculating Jaccard index

```

# Function to calculate Jaccard index
calculate_jaccard_index <- function(genes1, genes2) {
  genes1_set <- unique(strsplit(genes1, "\\|")[[1]])
  genes2_set <- unique(genes2)
  intersection <- length(intersect(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  union <- length(union(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  jaccard_index <- intersection/union
  return(jaccard_index)
}

# Function to calculate Jaccard scores for a given gene
# list

```

```

calculate_jaccard_scores <- function(cluster_genes, gene_lists) {
  gene_list_names <- unique(gene_lists$ListName)
  jaccard_scores <- map_df(gene_list_names, function(list_name) {
    genes_in_list <- gene_lists %>%
      filter(ListName == list_name) %>%
      pull(ENTREZID)
    score <- calculate_jaccard_index(cluster_genes, genes_in_list)
    tibble(Source = list_name, JaccardScore = score, Type = list_name)
  })
  return(jaccard_scores)
}

# Calculate Jaccard scores for curated gene lists
curated_jaccard_results <- SST_Geneinfo %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(cluster_genes = paste(unique(ENTREZID), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(curated_scores = map(cluster_genes, calculate_jaccard_scores,
    gene_lists)) %>%
  unnest(curated_scores)

# Calculate Jaccard scores for DisGeNET terms
dgn_jaccard_results <- SST_Geneinfo %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(cluster_genes = paste(unique(ENTREZID), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(dgn_scores = map(cluster_genes, function(genes) {
    DGN_results_TCSeg %>%
      mutate(JaccardScore = map_dbl(Genes, calculate_jaccard_index,
        genes2 = strsplit(genes, "\\|")[[1]])) %>%
      select(ID, JaccardScore) %>%
      rename(Source = ID) %>%
      mutate(Type = "DisGeNET")
  })) %>%
  unnest(dgn_scores)

# Combine curated and DGN results
combined_results <- bind_rows(curated_jaccard_results, dgn_jaccard_results)
# Convert cluster to factor and arrange levels
combined_results$cluster <- factor(combined_results$cluster,
  levels = paste0("Cluster_", 1:12))
# Check the combined results
print(head(combined_results))

```

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 5
##   cluster    cluster_genes      Source JaccardScore Type
##   <fct>      <chr>              <chr>      <dbl> <chr>
## 1 Cluster_1  368|2180|79611|79913|102|56999|100506125~ Neuro~    0.0179 Neur~
## 2 Cluster_1  368|2180|79611|79913|102|56999|100506125~ Neuro~    0.0161 Neur~
## 3 Cluster_1  368|2180|79611|79913|102|56999|100506125~ Psych~    0.0165 Psyc~
## 4 Cluster_10 5243|11194|5825|10061|55347|58527|29777|~ Neuro~    0.0222 Neur~
## 5 Cluster_10 5243|11194|5825|10061|55347|58527|29777|~ Neuro~    0.0137 Neur~
## 6 Cluster_10 5243|11194|5825|10061|55347|58527|29777|~ Psych~    0.0160 Psyc~

```

```
# Plotting Jaccard scores without separate panels
p <- ggplot(combined_results, aes(x = cluster, y = JaccardScore,
  color = Type)) + geom_jitter(alpha = 0.7, size = 3, width = 0.2,
  height = 0) + labs(title = "Jaccard Scores in SST Cell Clusters",
  subtitle = "Comparing Jaccard scores for DisGeNET terms and Curated Disease Gene Lists in Clusters",
  x = "SST Cluster", y = "Jaccard Score", color = "Gene List Source") +
  theme_minimal() + theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45,
  hjust = 1), plot.title = element_text(size = 22), plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 18),
  legend.title = element_text(size = 18), legend.text = element_text(size = 16),
  axis.title.x = element_text(size = 18), axis.title.y = element_text(size = 18),
  axis.text = element_text(size = 16)) + scale_color_manual(values = c(Neurodevelopmental = "#E66100",
  Neurological = "#5D3A9B", Psychiatric = "#15D3FF", DisGeNET = "lightgrey"))
```

p


```
ggsave("./results/paper_visualisations/2B_SST_Jaccard_DGN_Curdisgenes.pdf",
  p, dpi = 300, height = 10, width = 12)
```

2. For PN-dev cells

```
# Curated gene lists
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")
neuro1 <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neuro1_allgenes_list.txt")
```

```

psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
# Combine the gene lists into a single data frame with a
# 'ListName' column
gene_lists <- tibble(ENTREZID = as.numeric(c(neurodev, neurol,
  psych)), ListName = c(rep("Neurodevelopmental", length(neurodev)),
  rep("Neurological", length(neurol)), rep("Psychiatric", length(psych))))
# Read in PN-dev clusters PN dev TCSeq cluster info:
clusterinfo <- read.csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/PN_dev/PN_dev_clusterinfo")
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, Cluster = cluster)
clusterinfo <- rename(clusterinfo, cluster_size = num_genes)
PNdev_Geneinfo <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/PN_dev/PN_dev_Geneinfo")

# Read in HPO2gene, align with PN-dev HPO enrichments
phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("./HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt") %>%
  dplyr::select(-disease_id) %>%
  distinct()

id_to_name <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, hpo_name)

id_to_gene <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, ncbi_gene_id)

HPO_enrich <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust/20240606_HPO_summary.csv")
PNdev_subset <- HPO_enrich[grep("^PN_dev", HPO_enrich$Cluster),
  ]

HPO_descriptions <- HPO_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)
PNdev_HPO_terms <- PNdev_subset$ID

# Filter id_to_gene for PNdev HPO terms
PNdev_gene_lists <- id_to_gene %>%
  filter(hpo_id %in% PNdev_HPO_terms)

# Check the structure of the filtered gene lists
print(head(PNdev_gene_lists))

```

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 2
##   hpo_id      ncbi_gene_id
##   <chr>          <dbl>
## 1 HP:0011968      7360
## 2 HP:0011968      546
## 3 HP:0011968      5830
## 4 HP:0011968     10102
## 5 HP:0011968      7681
## 6 HP:0011968      3653

```

Calculate jaccard index

```

# Calculate Jaccard scores for curated gene lists
curated_jaccard_results <- PNdev_Geneinfo %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(cluster_genes = paste(unique(ENTREZID), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(curated_scores = map(cluster_genes, calculate_jaccard_scores,
    gene_lists)) %>%
  unnest(curated_scores)

# Calculate Jaccard scores for HPO terms
hpo_jaccard_results <- PNdev_Geneinfo %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(cluster_genes = paste(unique(ENTREZID), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(hpo_scores = map(cluster_genes, function(genes) {
    PNdev_gene_lists %>%
      filter(hpo_id %in% PNdev_HPO_terms) %>%
      group_by(hpo_id) %>%
      summarise(JaccardScore = calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
        ncbi_gene_id)) %>%
      rename(Source = hpo_id) %>%
      mutate(Type = "HPO")
  }))) %>%
  unnest(hpo_scores)

# Combine curated and HPO results
combined_results <- bind_rows(curated_jaccard_results, hpo_jaccard_results)

# Convert cluster to factor and arrange levels
combined_results$cluster <- factor(combined_results$cluster,
  levels = paste0("Cluster_", 1:12))

# Check the combined results
print(head(combined_results))

```

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 5
##   cluster      cluster_genes      Source JaccardScore Type
##   <fct>        <chr>                <chr>      <dbl> <chr>
## 1 Cluster_1  25980|23456|23|25841|390110|55331|70|102~ Neuro~      0.0206 Neur~
## 2 Cluster_1  25980|23456|23|25841|390110|55331|70|102~ Neuro~      0.0174 Neur~
## 3 Cluster_1  25980|23456|23|25841|390110|55331|70|102~ Psych~      0.0181 Psyc~
## 4 Cluster_10 5243|10257|145447|25|22885|38|93650|9397~ Neuro~      0.0194 Neur~
## 5 Cluster_10 5243|10257|145447|25|22885|38|93650|9397~ Neuro~      0.0227 Neur~
## 6 Cluster_10 5243|10257|145447|25|22885|38|93650|9397~ Psych~      0.0264 Psyc~

```

Plot jaccard scores

```

# Plotting Jaccard scores without separate panels
p <- ggplot(combined_results, aes(x = cluster, y = JaccardScore,
  color = Type)) + geom_jitter(alpha = 0.7, size = 3, width = 0.2,
  height = 0) + labs(title = "Jaccard Scores in PNdev Cell Clusters",
  subtitle = "Comparing Jaccard scores for HPO terms and Curated Disease Gene Lists in Clusters",
  x = "PNdev Cluster", y = "Jaccard Score", color = "Gene List Source") +
  theme_minimal() + theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45,
  hjust = 1), plot.title = element_text(size = 22), plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 18),

```

```

legend.title = element_text(size = 18), legend.text = element_text(size = 16),
axis.title.x = element_text(size = 18), axis.title.y = element_text(size = 18),
axis.text = element_text(size = 16)) + scale_color_manual(values = c(Neurodevelopmental = "#E66100",
Neurological = "#5D3A9B", Psychiatric = "#15D3FF", HPO = "lightgrey"))

```

p

Jaccard Scores in PNdev Cell Clusters

Comparing Jaccard scores for HPO terms and Curat


```

# Save the plot
ggsave("./results/paper_visualisations/2E_HPO_Jaccard_Curdisgenes.pdf",
  p, dpi = 300, height = 10, width = 12)

# Clean up
rm(list = ls())

```

2C,F: Time course plots

We will grab the timecourse analysis objects for each cell type and re-generate the plots with larger labels. Note, the next two code chunks have been modified to only run the first iteration so as to reduce the length of the knitted pdf. Note also that the combined plots are optimised for saving as individual files, so are not visually useful in this pdf.

```

outdir <- "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust"
celltypes <- list.dirs(path = outdir, full.names = FALSE, recursive = FALSE)
elements_2_remove = c("enrichment_summaries-old", "Intersects")
celltypes = celltypes[!(celltypes %in% elements_2_remove)]

```

```

# read in timecluster object, Prepare some gene information to append to cluster titles

# Uncomment the following line to run the code for every iteration
# for (cell in celltypes) {
# Only run the first iteration- comment the next two lines and uncomment the line above to run every it
for(i in seq_along(celltypes)) {
  if (i > 1) break # Only run for the first iteration

  cell <- celltypes[i]
  timeclustera <- readRDS(paste0(outdir, "/", cell, "/", cell, "timeclustera.RDS"))
  geneinfo <- data.frame(
    SYMBOL = names(timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster),
    cluster = timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster
  )

  symbol_to_entrez <- bitr(geneinfo$SYMBOL,
    fromType = "SYMBOL",
    toType = "ENTREZID",
    OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
    drop = FALSE) %>%

  group_by(SYMBOL) %>%
  slice(1) %>%
  ungroup()

  geneinfo <- full_join(geneinfo,
    symbol_to_entrez,
    by = "SYMBOL")

  clusterinfo <- geneinfo %>% # creates vector indicating number of genes in each cluster.
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(num_genes = n()) %>%
  arrange(cluster) %>%
  pull(num_genes)

  titles <- paste0("Cluster ", 1:length(clusterinfo),
    ". Number of genes: ", as.character(clusterinfo))
  # specify plot titles, including information about number of genes

  p <- timeclustplot(timeclustera,
    value = "z-score(PRKM)",
    cols = 2)

  plot_list_with_titles <- lapply(1:length(p), function(i) {
    p[[i]] +
    labs(title = titles[[i]]) +
    theme(
      plot.title = element_text(size = 30), # Adjust title size
      axis.title.x = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust x-axis title size
      axis.title.y = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust y-axis title size
      axis.text.x = element_text(size = 20), # Adjust x-axis text size
      axis.text.y = element_text(size = 20), # Adjust y-axis text size
      legend.title = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust legend title size
      legend.text = element_text(size = 20) # Adjust legend text size
    )
  })
}

```

```

    )
  })

  # just as an example of how these plots look:
  print(plot_list_with_titles[[1]])

  composite_plot <- wrap_plots(plot_list_with_titles,
                              ncol = 4)

  ggsave(paste0(outdir,"/",cell, "/", cell,"_TimeCoursePlot-resized.pdf"),
          composite_plot,
          height = 30,
          width = 64,
          limitsize = FALSE)
}

```


Cluster 1. Number of genes: 46

Making composite plots for each cell type and then one master pdf

```

outdir <- "./results/single_cell/TCSeq/cell_stage/2024/12_clust"
celltypes <- list.dirs(path = outdir, full.names = FALSE, recursive = FALSE)
elements_2_remove = c("enrichment_summaries-old", "Intersects")
celltypes = celltypes[!(celltypes %in% elements_2_remove)]

temp_pdf_files <- c()
# Uncomment the following line to run the code for every iteration
# for (cell in celltypes) {
# Only run the first iteration- comment the next two lines and uncomment the line above to run every it
for (i in seq_along(celltypes)) {
  if (i > 1) break # Stop after the first iteration

  cell <- celltypes[i]
  timeclustera <- readRDS(paste0(outdir, "/", cell, "/", cell, "timeclustera.RDS"))
  geneinfo <- data.frame(
    SYMBOL = names(timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster),
    cluster = timeclustera@clusterRes@cluster
  )

  symbol_to_entrez <- bitr(geneinfo$SYMBOL,
    fromType = "SYMBOL",
    toType = "ENTREZID",
    OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
    drop = FALSE) %>%

```

```

group_by(SYMBOL) %>%
dplyr::slice(1) %>%
ungroup()

geneinfo <- full_join(geneinfo,
                      symbol_to_entrez,
                      by = "SYMBOL")

clusterinfo <- geneinfo %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  summarise(num_genes = n()) %>%
  arrange(cluster) %>%
  pull(num_genes)

titles <- paste0("Cluster ", 1:length(clusterinfo),
                 ". Number of genes: ", as.character(clusterinfo))

p <- timeclustplot(timeclustera,
                  value = "z-score(PRKM)",
                  cols = 2)

plot_list_with_titles <- lapply(1:length(p), function(i) {
  p[[i]] +
  labs(title = titles[[i]]) +
  theme(
    plot.title = element_text(size = 30), # Adjust title size
    axis.title.x = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust x-axis title size
    axis.title.y = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust y-axis title size
    axis.text.x = element_text(size = 20), # Adjust x-axis text size
    axis.text.y = element_text(size = 20), # Adjust y-axis text size
    legend.title = element_text(size = 22), # Adjust legend title size
    legend.text = element_text(size = 20) # Adjust legend text size
  )
})

# Create a composite plot for each cell type and add a title
composite_plot <- wrap_plots(plot_list_with_titles, ncol = 4) +
  plot_annotation(title = paste0(cell, ": Temporal Expression Clusters"),
                 theme = theme(plot.title = element_text(size = 40, face = "bold")))

# Save the composite plot to a temporary PDF file
temp_pdf_file <- paste0(outdir, "/", cell, "_temp.pdf")
temp_pdf_files <- c(temp_pdf_files, temp_pdf_file)
ggsave(temp_pdf_file, composite_plot, height = 29.4, width = 64, limitsize = FALSE)
}

```



```

"Reduced tendon reflexes", "Ventriculomegaly")

data <- HPO_enrichments %>%
  filter(Description %in% terms) %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "))
# Add module size information: need size for: VIP black (1
# entry), L2/3 CUX2 magenta (9), L2/3 CUX2 salmon (5);
# given small number of rows, will just do manually.
clusterSizes <- rep(c("(156 genes)", "(90 genes)", "(58 genes)"),
  times = c(1, 9, 5))

data <- data %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "), combined_label = paste(cell_type,
    clusterSizes, sep = " - "), label_with_break = gsub(" - ",
    " \n", combined_label)) # Combine cell_type with extra data
unique_labels <- unique(data$label_with_break)
data$label_with_break <- factor(data$label_with_break, levels = sort(unique(data$label_with_break)))

plot <- ggplot(data = data, aes(x = label_with_break, y = Description,
  fill = "lightseagreen")) + scale_fill_manual(values = "lightseagreen") +
  geom_tile(width = 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45,
  hjust = 1, vjust = 1, size = 20), axis.text.y = element_text(size = 20),
  plot.title = element_text(size = 26, face = "bold", vjust = 1),
  legend.position = "none", plot.title.position = "plot", plot.margin = unit(c(0.2,
    0.75, 0, 0.75), "inches")) + ggtitle("HPO Term Enrichments in Gene Co-expression Modules") +
  ylab(NULL) + xlab(NULL) + scale_x_discrete(expand = c(0,
  0)) + scale_y_discrete(expand = c(0, 0)) + scale_y_discrete(labels = label_wrap_gen(width = 36)) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = rep(1:length(unique(data$Description)),
  each = 2) - 0.5, linewidth = 0.8) + geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1,
  to = length(unique(data$cell_type)), by = 5) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.8) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1, to = length(unique(data$cell_type)),
  by = 1) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.1) + scale_x_discrete()

plot

```

HPO Term Enrichments in Gene Co-expression Modules


```
ggsave(plot, filename = paste0("./results/paper_visualisations/3A_HPO_enrichment_tile.pdf"),
        width = 12, height = 10, dpi = 300)
rm(list = ls())
```

```
outdir <- "./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"

DGN_enrichments <- read_csv(paste0(outdir, "20240221_DGN_enrichments_summary_Jaccard.csv"))

terms <- c("Agenesis of corpus callosum", "Autonomic nervous system disorders",
          "Cerebral ventriculomegaly", "Dystrophia myotonica 2", "Frontotemporal Lobar Degeneration",
          "Hydrocephalus", "Neurofibromatoses", "Neurofibromatosis 1",
          "Seizures, Focal", "Specific learning disability", "Substance Withdrawal Syndrome")

data <- DGN_enrichments %>%
  filter(Description %in% terms) %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "))

# Add cluster size information: need cluster size for: L5/6
# THEMIS yellow (6), ID2_black (1), L4 RORB blue (2),
# Astro_turquoise (1), L2-3 CUX2 magenta (1)
```

```

clusterSizes <- rep(c("(168 genes)", "(100 genes)", "(298 genes)",
  "(1327 genes)", "(90 genes)"), times = c(6, 1, 2, 1, 1))

data <- data %>%
  mutate(cell_type = str_replace_all(Cluster, "_", " "), combined_label = paste(cell_type,
    clusterSizes, sep = " - "), label_with_break = gsub(" - ",
    " \n", combined_label)) # Combine cell_type with extra data
unique_labels <- unique(data$label_with_break)
data$label_with_break <- factor(data$label_with_break, levels = sort(unique(data$label_with_break)))

plot <- ggplot(data = data, aes(x = label_with_break, y = Description,
  fill = "seagreen")) + geom_tile(width = 1) + theme_classic() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1,
    size = 20), axis.text.y = element_text(size = 20), plot.title = element_text(size = 26,
    face = "bold", vjust = 1), legend.position = "none",
    plot.title.position = "plot", plot.margin = unit(c(0.2,
    0.75, 0, 0.75), "inches")) + ggtitle("DisGeNET Enrichments in Gene Co-expression Modules") +
  ylab(NULL) + xlab(NULL) + scale_x_discrete(expand = c(0,
  0)) + scale_y_discrete(expand = c(0, 0)) + scale_y_discrete(labels = label_wrap_gen(width = 22)) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = rep(1:length(unique(data$Description)),
    each = 2) - 0.5, linewidth = 0.8) + geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1,
  to = length(unique(data$cell_type)), by = 5) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.8) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = (seq(from = 1, to = length(unique(data$cell_type)),
    by = 1) - 0.5), linewidth = 0.1) + scale_x_discrete()

plot

```

DisGeNET Enrichments in Gene Co-expression Modules


```
ggsave(plot, filename = paste0("results/paper_visualisations/3B_DGN_enrichment_tile.pdf"),
        width = 12, height = 10, dpi = 300)
rm(list = ls())
```

3C: Disease gene list Jaccard scores

Read in the required data: L2-3 CUX2 modules, Curated disease gene lists, HPO2gene, DisGeNET data.

```
# Load the modules information
modules_info <- read.csv("./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/L2-3_CUX2/L2-3_CUX2Modules.csv")
modules_info <- modules_info %>%
  filter(module != "grey") %>%
  select(gene_name, module)

# Load curated disease gene lists
neurodev <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurodev_allgenes_list.txt")
neurol <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/neurol_allgenes_list.txt")
psych <- readLines("./scratch/sanitycheck/Entrez_genelist/psych_allgenes_list.txt")
gene_lists <- tibble(ENTREZID = as.numeric(c(neurodev, neurol,
```

```

psych)), ListName = c(rep("Neurodevelopmental", length(neurodev)),
  rep("Neurological", length(neuro1)), rep("Psychiatric", length(psych))))

# Read in HPO2gene, align with enriched HPO terms
phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("./HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt") %>%
  dplyr::select(-disease_id) %>%
  distinct()

id_to_name <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, hpo_name)

id_to_gene <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, ncbi_gene_id)

# Load HPO enrichments
HPO_enrich <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/20240424_HPO_enrichments_summary")
HPO_enrich <- HPO_enrich %>%
  filter(grepl("^L2-3_CUX2", Cluster))
HPO_descriptions <- HPO_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)

# Load DisGeNET enrichments
DGN_enrich <- read_csv("./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/20240424_DGN_enrichments_summary")
DGN_enrich <- DGN_enrich %>%
  filter(grepl("^L2-3_CUX2", Cluster))
DGN_descriptions <- DGN_enrich %>%
  dplyr::select(ID, Description)
L2_3_CUX2_DGN_terms <- DGN_enrich$ID

# Process DGN Enrichment with Full Gene List for Each Term
data("DGN_PATHID2EXTID")
large_list_df <- map_df(names(DGN_PATHID2EXTID), ~tibble(ID = .x,
  Genes = list(DGN_PATHID2EXTID[[.x]])))
DGN_results <- large_list_df %>%
  filter(ID %in% L2_3_CUX2_DGN_terms) %>%
  mutate(Genes = map_chr(Genes, ~paste(.x, collapse = "|")))

# Filter id_to_gene for relevant HPO terms
HPO_terms <- HPO_enrich$ID
HPO_gene_lists <- id_to_gene %>%
  filter(hpo_id %in% HPO_terms)

# Check the structure of the filtered gene lists
print(head(HPO_gene_lists))

```

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 2
##   hpo_id      ncbi_gene_id
##   <chr>          <dbl>
## 1 HP:0011314      4591
## 2 HP:0011314     118429
## 3 HP:0011314      5896
## 4 HP:0011314      5897
## 5 HP:0011314     64421

```

Calculate Jaccard index

```

# Function to calculate Jaccard index
calculate_jaccard_index <- function(genes1, genes2) {
  genes1_set <- unique(strsplit(genes1, "\\|")[[1]])
  genes2_set <- unique(genes2)
  intersection <- length(intersect(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  union <- length(union(genes1_set, genes2_set))
  jaccard_index <- intersection/union
  return(jaccard_index)
}

# Function to calculate Jaccard scores for a given gene
# list
calculate_jaccard_scores <- function(module_genes, gene_lists) {
  gene_list_names <- unique(gene_lists$ListName)
  jaccard_scores <- map_df(gene_list_names, function(list_name) {
    genes_in_list <- gene_lists %>%
      filter(ListName == list_name) %>%
      pull(ENTREZID)
    score <- calculate_jaccard_index(module_genes, genes_in_list)
    tibble(Source = list_name, JaccardScore = score, Type = list_name)
  })
  return(jaccard_scores)
}

# Calculate Jaccard scores for curated gene lists
curated_jaccard_results <- modules_info %>%
  group_by(module) %>%
  summarise(module_genes = paste(unique(gene_name), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(curated_scores = map(module_genes, calculate_jaccard_scores,
    gene_lists)) %>%
  unnest(curated_scores)

# Calculate Jaccard scores for HPO terms
hpo_jaccard_results <- modules_info %>%
  group_by(module) %>%
  summarise(module_genes = paste(unique(gene_name), collapse = "|")) %>%
  mutate(hpo_scores = map(module_genes, function(genes) {
    HPO_gene_lists %>%
      filter(hpo_id %in% HPO_terms) %>%
      group_by(hpo_id) %>%
      summarise(JaccardScore = calculate_jaccard_index(genes,
        ncbi_gene_id)) %>%
      rename(Source = hpo_id) %>%
      mutate(Type = "HPO")
  })) %>%
  unnest(hpo_scores)

# Calculate Jaccard scores for DisGeNET terms
dgn_jaccard_results <- modules_info %>%
  group_by(module) %>%

```

```

summarise(module_genes = paste(unique(gene_name), collapse = "|")) %>%
mutate(dgn_scores = map(module_genes, function(genes) {
  DGN_results %>%
    filter(ID %in% L2_3_CUX2_DGN_terms) %>%
    mutate(JaccardScore = map_dbl(Genes, calculate_jaccard_index,
      genes2 = strsplit(genes, "\\|")[[1]])) %>%
    select(ID, JaccardScore) %>%
    rename(Source = ID) %>%
    mutate(Type = "DisGeNET")
})) %>%
unnest(dgn_scores)

# Combine curated, HPO, and DisGeNET results
combined_results <- bind_rows(curated_jaccard_results, hpo_jaccard_results,
  dgn_jaccard_results)

# Convert module to factor and arrange levels
combined_results$module <- factor(combined_results$module, levels = unique(modules_info$module))

# Check the combined results
print(head(combined_results))

```

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 5
##   module module_genes           Source JaccardScore Type
##   <fct> <chr>                   <chr>         <dbl> <chr>
## 1 black  81569|84970|22887|388630|5733|110806286|1053~ Neuro~      0.00528 Neur~
## 2 black  81569|84970|22887|388630|5733|110806286|1053~ Neuro~      0.00415 Neur~
## 3 black  81569|84970|22887|388630|5733|110806286|1053~ Psych~      0.00802 Psyc~
## 4 blue   29101|23463|55450|712|100129196|79570|127544~ Neuro~      0.0160  Neur~
## 5 blue   29101|23463|55450|712|100129196|79570|127544~ Neuro~      0.00768 Neur~
## 6 blue   29101|23463|55450|712|100129196|79570|127544~ Psych~      0.0189  Psyc~

```

Plot scores

```

# Plotting Jaccard scores without separate panels
p <- ggplot(combined_results, aes(x = module, y = JaccardScore, color = Type)) +
  geom_jitter(alpha = 0.7, size = 3, width = 0.3, height = 0) +
  labs(
    title = "Jaccard Scores in Co-expression Modules",
    #subtitle = "Comparing Jaccard scores for HPO and DisGeNET terms, and Curated Disease Gene Lists in",
    x = "Module",
    y = "Jaccard Score",
    color = "Gene List Source"
  ) +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(
    axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1),
    plot.title = element_text(size = 22, face = "bold"),
    plot.subtitle = element_text(size = 16),
    legend.title = element_text(size = 18),
    legend.text = element_text(size = 16),
    legend.position = "bottom",
    axis.title.x = element_blank(),

```

```

axis.title.y = element_text(size = 18),
axis.text = element_text(size = 16)
) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("Neurodevelopmental" = "#E66100",
                              "Neurological" = "#5D3A9B",
                              "Psychiatric" = "#15D3FF",
                              "HPO" = "lightgrey",
                              "DisGeNET" = "#000000"))

```

p

Jaccard Scores in Co-expression Modu

Source ● DisGeNET ● HPO ● Neurodevelopmental ● Neuro

```

# Save the plot
ggsave("./results/paper_visualisations/3C_HPO_DGN_Jaccard_Curdisgenes.pdf", p, dpi = 300, height = 8, width = 12)

# Clean up
rm(list = ls())

```

3D: stage composition of modules

```

#read in the ME RDSs
CUX2MEs <- readRDS("./results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/L2-3_CUX2/L2-3_CUX2Module_connectivity.rds")
MEs <- GetMEs(CUX2MEs) %>%
  dplyr::select(!grey) # Retrieve ME information, minus the grey module (grey = genes not assigned to a module)

```

```

metadata.celltypes <- CUX2MEs@meta.data %>%
  dplyr::select(stage_id) %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "sample") # begin by processing metadata a little to make life more convenient

MEs.edited <- MEs %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "sample") %>%
  left_join(metadata.celltypes,
            by = "sample") # append metadata to ME information

# Next is to extract information specific for each module
ME.cell.associations <- list() # initialize empty list
ME.cell.associations <- lapply(colnames(MEs),
                              FUN = function(x){
                                df <- MEs.edited %>%
                                  dplyr::select(any_of(x), sample, stage_id) %>% # only look at one module
                                  arrange(desc(get(x))) %>% # the value under each module is the ME. This arrangement
                                  slice_head(n = 500) # extract the top n entries, as specified by the user
                                ME.cell.associations[[x]] <- df # append the created dataframe to the object
                              })

names(ME.cell.associations) <- colnames(MEs)

MEs.means <- MEs.edited %>%
  group_by(stage_id) %>%
  summarise(across(.cols = where(is.numeric), ~ mean(., na.rm = TRUE))) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = where(is.numeric),
               names_to = "module",
               values_to = "ME") %>%
  mutate(ME = ifelse(ME < 0, 0, ME))
module_colours <- unique(MEs.means$module)
names(module_colours) <- module_colours
# Ensure the stage_id is ordered correctly in the data frame
custom_order <- c("Fetal", "Neonatal", "Infancy", "Childhood", "Adolescence", "Adult")
MEs.means$stage_id <- factor(MEs.means$stage_id, levels = custom_order)

# Pivot and create a matrix ensuring that stages are columns in the correct order
m_df <- pivot_wider(MEs.means, names_from = "stage_id", values_from = "ME", names_sort = TRUE)

# Explicitly convert values to numeric to ensure matrix is numeric
m_df[-1] <- lapply(m_df[-1], as.numeric)

# Convert to matrix
m <- as.matrix(m_df[-1]) # Exclude the first column for the matrix conversion

# Assign row names from the first column of m_df which contains the module names
rownames(m) <- m_df[[1]]

# Define the layout matrix for the heatmap and color key
lmat <- rbind(c(0, 3), # Column dendrogram (not used, hence 0)
             c(2, 1), # Heatmap and row dendrogram
             c(0, 4)) # Color key (below the heatmap)

# Define the widths and heights

```

```

lwid <- c(0.05, 4) # Widths for row dendrogram and heatmap
lhei <- c(0.5, 4, 1) # Heights for column dendrogram, heatmap, and color key

# Plot the heatmap

pdf("./results/paper_visualisations/3D_L23CUX2_Module_stage_importance.pdf",width = 20, height = 8)
par(cex.axis = 1.5)
x <- heatmap.2(m,
  main = "Developmental Stage Importance in Co-expression Modules",
  xlab = "Developmental Stage",
  ylab = "Module",
  scale = "row",
  key = TRUE,
  symkey = FALSE,
  density.info = "none",
  trace = "none",
  Colv = NA, # No column dendrogram
  Rowv = NA, # Row dendrogram to cluster modules
  dendrogram = "none",
  col = viridis,
  margins = c(10, 15), # Adjust margins to fit labels
  cexRow = 1.5,
  cexCol = 1.5,
  cex.main = 7,
  cex.lab = 6,
  lmat = lmat,
  lwid = lwid,
  lhei = lhei)
dev.off()

```

```

## pdf
## 2

```

```
print(x)
```

```

## $rowInd
## [1] 14 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
##
## $colInd
## [1] 1 2 3 4 5 6
##
## $call
## heatmap.2(x = m, Rowv = NA, Colv = NA, dendrogram = "none", scale = "row",
## col = viridis, trace = "none", margins = c(10, 15), cexRow = 1.5,
## cexCol = 1.5, key = TRUE, density.info = "none", symkey = FALSE,
## main = "Developmental Stage Importance in Co-expression Modules",
## xlab = "Developmental Stage", ylab = "Module", lmat = lmat,
## lhei = lhei, lwid = lwid, cex.main = 7, cex.lab = 6)
##
## $rowMeans
##      red      pink      brown  turquoise      blue      cyan
## 1.2895387 0.6605217 2.3975485 1.3486841 1.7738748 0.3018599
##  salmon greenyellow      purple      black      yellow      green

```

```

## 0.8707609 0.4515916 0.5936974 2.1258575 3.7259487 1.2333454
## tan magenta
## 0.9386323 0.3836726
##
## $rowSDs
## red pink brown turquoise blue cyan
## 2.5435341 1.0893439 3.5158919 2.3502291 3.0005862 0.4200339
## salmon greenyellow purple black yellow green
## 1.3083640 0.4959554 0.9983533 2.1090561 4.7252463 1.1531997
## tan magenta
## 1.9294871 0.9398020
##
## $carpet
## red pink brown turquoise blue cyan
## Fetal -0.50698698 -0.6063482 1.4506931 1.8716948 -0.4390995 0.38868446
## Neonatal 1.99263897 1.9040573 1.1109814 0.4237139 1.9159012 -0.71865607
## Infancy 0.03530896 -0.6063482 -0.5159217 -0.5738522 0.2967266 -0.71865607
## Childhood -0.50698698 -0.4085513 -0.6819176 -0.5738522 -0.5911761 -0.71865607
## Adolescence -0.50698698 0.3235387 -0.6819176 -0.5738522 -0.5911761 -0.04852734
## Adult -0.50698698 -0.6063482 -0.6819176 -0.5738522 -0.5911761 1.81581108
## salmon greenyellow purple black yellow green
## Fetal -0.6655342 -0.9105487 -0.5946767 -1.0079663 -0.7885195 -1.0694986
## Neonatal -0.6655342 -0.9105487 -0.5946767 -1.0079663 -0.7885195 0.7238186
## Infancy -0.5315265 1.0253844 -0.5946767 -0.6248073 -0.7885195 1.0660039
## Childhood -0.6655342 -0.9105487 -0.5946767 0.4731167 -0.1243086 0.8810685
## Adolescence 0.9534571 0.9061657 0.5744079 1.0364359 1.1460911 -0.5386044
## Adult 1.5746720 0.8000961 1.8042988 1.1311874 1.3437759 -1.0627881
## tan magenta
## Fetal -0.48646724 -0.4082483
## Neonatal -0.48646724 -0.4082483
## Infancy -0.48646724 2.0412415
## Childhood -0.48646724 -0.4082483
## Adolescence -0.06634301 -0.4082483
## Adult 2.01221199 -0.4082483
##
## $rowDendrogram
## 'dendrogram' with 2 branches and 14 members total, at height 1.414214
##
## $colDendrogram
## 'dendrogram' with 2 branches and 6 members total, at height 1.414214
##
## $breaks
## [1] -2.0412415 -1.7690759 -1.4969104 -1.2247449 -0.9525793 -0.6804138
## [7] -0.4082483 -0.1360828 0.1360828 0.4082483 0.6804138 0.9525793
## [13] 1.2247449 1.4969104 1.7690759 2.0412415
##
## $col
## [1] "#440154FF" "#481B6DFF" "#46337EFF" "#3F4889FF" "#365C8DFF" "#2E6E8EFF"
## [7] "#277F8EFF" "#21908CFF" "#1FA187FF" "#2DB27DFF" "#4AC16DFF" "#71CF57FF"
## [13] "#9FDA3AFF" "#CFE11CFF" "#FDE725FF"
##
## $colorTable
## low high color
## 1 -2.0412415 -1.7690759 #440154FF

```

```
## 2 -1.7690759 -1.4969104 #481B6DFF
## 3 -1.4969104 -1.2247449 #46337EFF
## 4 -1.2247449 -0.9525793 #3F4889FF
## 5 -0.9525793 -0.6804138 #365C8DFF
## 6 -0.6804138 -0.4082483 #2E6E8EFF
## 7 -0.4082483 -0.1360828 #277F8EFF
## 8 -0.1360828 0.1360828 #21908CFF
## 9 0.1360828 0.4082483 #1FA187FF
## 10 0.4082483 0.6804138 #2DB27DFF
## 11 0.6804138 0.9525793 #4AC16DFF
## 12 0.9525793 1.2247449 #71CF57FF
## 13 1.2247449 1.4969104 #9FDA3AFF
## 14 1.4969104 1.7690759 #CFE11CFF
## 15 1.7690759 2.0412415 #FDE725FF
##
## $layout
## $layout$lmat
##      [,1] [,2]
## [1,]    0    3
## [2,]    2    1
## [3,]    0    4
##
## $layout$lhei
## [1] 0.5 4.0 1.0
##
## $layout$lwid
## [1] 0.05 4.00
```